

An experimental setup for power loss measurement up to 1 kHz using an Epstein frame at CMI

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Abstract: This paper presents a description of an experimental setup used at the Czech Metrology Institute (CMI) for measuring the specific power loss of oriented and non-oriented electrical steel sheets up to 1 kHz using an Epstein frame. Special attention is given a) to the description of the hardware that is used, b) to a description of the feedback control and measurement software, and c) to the analysis of sources of uncertainty, and to validation. Calibration expanded uncertainty of (0.5 up to 1.6) % for $k = 2$ can be achieved by this setup.

Keywords: Epstein, feedback, measurement, power loss, reference sample, uncertainty.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electrical steel is used for transformers or motors and for generators. The total power loss is therefore an important parameter for determining the efficiency of the material. Two methods are used for such measurements - the Epstein frame and the Single Sheet Tester (SST). Both methods are defined by the IEC standards [1, 2]. CMI as a national metrology institute has always provided measurements of the total losses in electrical steels with a given metrological traceability using the Epstein frame. However, the setup could be used for measurements at 50 Hz or 60 Hz only. Due to several requests for measurements of the total loss also at higher frequencies than 50/60 Hz (up to 1 kHz), a new setup was needed. There are of course commercial automated setups for such measurements, e.g. MPG 200 (Brockhaus Messtechnik), MAG-RJJ-6.0 (R&J Measurement), REMACOMP C-1200 / C-2200 (Magnet-Physik) or the AMH permeameter type (Laboratorio Elettrofisico). However, these systems are not cheap, because they can also be used for other measurements (depending on the accessories), and not only for total power loss measurements with an Epstein frame. A new experimental setup for specific total power loss measurements using an Epstein frame was therefore implemented within the HEFMAG project at CMI.

2. SUBJECT & METHODS

A. Hardware description

Fig.1 shows the block diagram of the total power loss measurement using an Epstein frame at CMI. The generated analog signal (DAC out) from the DAQ is fed back to the analog DAQ input for sampling synchronization (ADC readback), and to the power amplifier that feeds the primary winding of the Epstein frame (DUT). The flowing current is measured using a current shunt R and an analog DAQ input (ADC-H). The induced voltage u_B from the secondary winding is applied to the differential input of the PA01 programmable signal attenuator (home built), because the induced voltage can exceed the maximum range A/D inputs DAQ, which is ± 10 V. The attenuator converts the differential

signal into a signal with a common ground, workable DAQ. Attenuation is selectable in four levels (1, 5, 20 and 100) using a combination of two optically separated digital inputs. Then the attenuator is applied to the analog DAQ input (ADC-B). The digitized current (as voltage drop u_H on the current shunt) through the primary winding, the voltage u_B on the secondary winding and the back-read generated signal entering the power amplifier are read from the DAQ by a control software in the computer. The DAQ is a multipurpose USB-6281 (NI) with an 18-bit A/D converter and an aggregate sampling rate of 500 kS/s, a 16-bit DAC, and a set of generic digital I/O ports. The model 7228 (AE Techtron) power amplifier supplies the primary winding of the Epstein frame (700 turns realized by CMI or 100 turns from Brockhaus Messtechnik).

The basis of the signal part of PA01 is the OPA192 operational amplifier, connected as a differential amplifier. It converts the input differential signal into an output signal with a common ground. With the help of three relays with a switching contact, the resistor in the feedback of the amplifier is changed, which determines its attenuation. It is always assumed that one relay or no relay is closed. This makes it possible to achieve one of the four attenuation values, namely, 1, 5, 20 or 100. Thin-film resistors with a tolerance of 0.1 % are used in the signal part. For alternating signals, PA01 behaves as a first-order low-pass filter. The cut-off frequency varies according to the attenuation setting, and the cut-off frequency increases as the attenuation increases. The measured frequency characteristic of PA01 is embedded as a *.json* file that provides a table of data for each nominal gain (attenuation) setting where, for a certain range of discrete frequencies, a pair of gain/phase values is assigned to each frequency value. It is assumed that the DC gain and phase are equal to the gain and phase of the lowest frequency in the table. The frequency response of points that do not directly coincide with any point in the table is calculated by linear interpolation of two directly adjacent points from the table to

Fig. 1. Block diagram for measurements of magnetic losses in electrical steel sheets at CMI using an Epstein frame.

the desired point.

B. Feedback control and measurement software

According to IEC 60404-2 [1], the shape factor of the sine wave signal on the secondary of the Epstein frame must be maintained at $1.11 \pm 1\%$. This means that feedback control must be applied. Several papers have been published on this topic, which solve the feedback control with various variations by the iterative method using controllers [3], [4], [5], by checking the THD parameter [6] or by the method of harmonic compensation [7]. The iterative method with the proportional controller was used for its easy implementation. Software for feedback control and for measurements of total loss was written in the C# programming language on the .NET Framework 4.8 using the Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF) graphics libraries.

A block diagram of the iterative loop is presented in Fig. 2. The primal generated signal is created as a set of discrete samples that corresponds to one period of cosine signal at a fundamental frequency f_0 , with an amplitude determined by the user. The number of signal samples shall be determined according to

$$n_g = \frac{f_s}{f_0}, \quad (1)$$

where n_g is the number of samples generated and f_s is the sampling rate of the DAC. At the same time, a set of samples is created representing one period of the target signal from the secondary winding, again as a cosine at a fundamental frequency with an amplitude calculated as the arithmetic mean of the user-defined range of the target amplitude. The iteration loop begins with the loading of the generated signal into the DAQ. Subsequently, the system waits for the system

to stabilize for a time corresponding to the specified number of periods of the input signal. Then the signal is sampled from three channels – the reverse reading of the generated signal, the current through the primary winding, and the voltage on the secondary winding. The number of samples of each channel n_s is equal for all three channels, and corresponds to the entire number of periods n_p entered by the user, according to

$$n_s = \frac{n_p f_s}{f_0}. \quad (2)$$

If a preamplifier is selected for the primary current and/or for the secondary voltage signal, the measured signal is converted to the original signal from the primary and/or secondary winding. The method of conversion varies according to the type of preamplifier, and from the iteration loop point of view it is viewed as a black box that converts a set of samples from the A/D converter into a set of samples of the original signal, based only on knowledge of the samples themselves and the sampling rate. For a theoretical constant-gain preamplifier, a simple division of each sample by a gain is used. For the PA01 preamplifier, the signal conversion method for a linear amplifier with a known frequency response is used. The signal is further averaged into the number of samples corresponding to one period (according to f_0). Subsequently, a smoothing FIR filter is applied to each channel, the coefficients of which are determined by the user.

For all manipulations with the signal, it is assumed that the signal is periodic, and if samples preceding (following) one period are needed for the calculation (e.g. FIR filter), samples from the end (beginning) of the same data set are used. The following iteration is calculated using the principle of the classical proportional controller.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the iterative loop.

However, before the calculation, a phased alignment is performed. Due to the physical nature of magnetic polarization J_m and due to the real elements of the measuring chain that is used, the phases of the measured signal are shifted relative to the generated signal. To calculate the next iteration, it is first necessary to shift the phase – align the samples – so that the individual data sets are not phase-shifted relative to each other. Using the discrete Fourier transform, the value of the voltage phase on the secondary winding at the fundamental frequency is obtained. The target signal sample set shall be rearranged so that its phase coincides with that of the signal from the secondary winding. The phase of the generated signal from the readback channel is also determined, and the output samples from the current iteration are phased aligned to the phase identical to that of the generated signal. This removes any asynchronicity of the generated signal with respect to the sampled signals. The proportional controller calculates each sample of the output signal of the following iteration (o_{i+1}) in turn using formula (3), where t is the phase-aligned target signal, s_s is the phase-aligned, averaged and filtered voltage signal from the secondary winding, K_P is the user-selected amplification factor of the regulator, and o_i is the output signal of the current iteration. The *RMS* index indicates the mean square value of the signal.

$$o_{i+1} = \frac{(t-s_s)K_P o_{i,RMS}}{s_{s,RMS}} + o_i. \quad (3)$$

The DC component is removed from the new output signal o_{i+1} by subtracting from each sample the arithmetic mean value of all samples. The shape factor of the voltage on the secondary winding, which is one of the target metrics, is calculated as the quotient of the mean quadratic value and the average absolute value of the signal. The amplitude of magnetic polarization or specific magnetic loss is calculated using equation A.2 or A.3, from Appendix A of International Standard IEC 60404-2 [1].

Using the given SW, it is possible to set all parameters of the iteration loop (feedback), the parameters of the measured sample, and to determine the value of the total losses of the measured sample, including the uncertainty. The software also displays the primary and secondary waveforms and the shape factor value of the secondary voltage.

C. Uncertainty analysis

The uncertainty of the total loss measurement using the described setup depends mainly on the uncertainty of the frequency, on the u_H and u_B measurements, on the uncertainty of the current shunt value that is used, on the repeatability and on the uncertainty of the PA01 attenuator. The measured (calibrated) frequency characteristic of PA01 is applied in the *.json* file in the control software, so the correction of PA01 can be made.

Table 1. Example of the uncertainty budget using the CMI setup for power loss measurements at 50 Hz.

Source of uncertainty	Type of uncertainty	k-factor	standard uncertainty (%)
current shunt value	B	1	0.005
voltage u_B (DAQ)	B	1	0.05
voltage u_H (DAQ)	B	1	0.05
attenuator PA01	B	1	0.2
Frequency	B	1	0.01
temperature influence	B	1	0.05
mismatch	B	1	0.06
uncertainty of the Epstein frame and the sample			
set value of J_m	B	1	0.05
repeatability	A	1	0.1
total uncertainty	-	1	0.25
total expanded uncertainty	-	2	0.5

Table 2. Example of the uncertainty budget using the CMI setup for power loss measurements at 1000 Hz.

Source of uncertainty	Type of uncertainty	k-factor	standard uncertainty (%)
current shunt value	B	1	0.02
voltage u_B (DAQ)	B	1	0.10
voltage u_H (DAQ)	B	1	0.10
attenuator PA01	B	1	0.70
frequency	B	1	0.01
temperature influence	B	1	0.05
mismatch	B	1	0.06
uncertainty of the Epstein frame and the sample			
set value of J_m	B	1	0.05
repeatability	A	1	0.35
total uncertainty	-	1	0.80
total expanded uncertainty	-	2	1.6

The other sources of uncertainties, which were determined experimentally, are the influence of temperature and the mismatch uncertainty of the Epstein frame and the sample. The uncertainty budget for the loss measurement by the Epstein frame using the CMI setup is shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

D. Validation

The setup described above was validated by two methods. First, the measurement of the total loss of the Epstein sample was cross-validated using measurement software and TracePQM WattMeter (TWM), with the use of two 3458A-type multimeters. TWM was realized within the TracePQM

project [8]. The power value P measured by TWM (using the TWM-PWRTDI time domain integration method) was then divided by the effective mass m_a of the Epstein sample to get the specific total loss value P_s

$$P_s = \frac{P}{m_a} \text{ (W/kg)}. \quad (4)$$

Second, the setup was compared with the setups of other HEFMAG project participants - PTB Germany, INRIM Italy, NPL United Kingdom and UNOTT (University of Nottingham) United Kingdom - using several Epstein samples of grain-oriented (GO) and non-oriented (NO) electrical steel sheets. Due to the large amount of measured data, only the results from one GO sample and from one NO sample at two frequencies (50 Hz and 1000 Hz for the GO sample and 50 Hz and 400 Hz for the NO sample) at the maximum value of J_m will be presented here. The parameters of the Epstein samples are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Parameters of the Epstein samples

Sample	Density (kg/m ³)	Cross section ($\times 10^{-5}$ m ²)	Weight (kg)	Number of strips
NO 0.3	7600	2.64974	0.24140	12
GO 0.18	7650	2.61590	0.25640	20
		2.09280	0.20504	16

3. RESULTS

Samples with parameters according to Table 3. were used to validate the described setup. Results of cross-validation using the TWM tool are presented in Table 4., where f is frequency, P_{s1} is the value measured by the CMI setup and $U(P_{s1})$ is its relative expanded uncertainty (k=2), P_{s2} is the value measured by the TWM tool and $U(P_{s2})$ is its relative expanded uncertainty, and δ_r is the relative difference between P_{s1} and P_{s2} . The results are in good agreement - the relative differences are within the stated expanded uncertainties of the values measured by the CMI setup.

Table 4. Results of cross-validation using the TWM tool

Sample	f (Hz)	P_{s1} (W/kg)	$U(P_{s1})$ (%)	P_{s2} (W/kg)	$U(P_{s2})$ (%)	δ_r (%)
NO 0.3	50	2.158	0.80	2.146	0.46	-0.54
	400	28.46	1.3	28.801	0.30	1.19
GO 0.18	50		0.50	0.9262	0.42	-0.31
		0.9290				
	400	19.46	0.60	19.520	0.22	0.29
	1000	27.11	1.0	27.303	0.15	0.73

For all measurements, the evaluation of the HEFMAG comparison was performed following procedure B in [9]. Based on the power loss data and their uncertainties from all participants, the reference value and its uncertainty (including other necessary characteristics) were calculated using the M-P (Mandel-Paul) mean [10]. The graphs results of the HEFMAG round robin comparison of the two described samples can be found in Fig. 3, Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, where the red line is the reference value, the red dashed lines are the border of the reference value expanded uncertainty, the blue star is the point measured by the participant, and the blue lines are the expanded uncertainties of the measured values. The

results are in good agreement, as can be seen from the graphs.

Fig. 3. Comparison result of sample NO 0.3 at $J_m=1.5$ T and 50 Hz.

Fig. 6. Comparison result of sample GO 0.18 at $J_m=1.0$ T and 1000 Hz.

Fig. 4. Comparison result of sample NO 0.3 at $J_m=1.4$ T and 400 Hz.

Fig. 5. Comparison result of sample GO 0.18 at $J_m=1.8$ T and 50 Hz.

4. CONCLUSION

A new experimental setup for the total loss of electrical steel sheets using an Epstein frame at CMI has been described. The hardware, feedback control and measurement software, and also the uncertainty analysis have been described in detail. The total loss measurement with the new software was validated by a comparison with TWM software using two 3458A type multimeters, and by a comparison of reference samples, which were measured by INRIM, NPL, PTB and UNOTT within the HEFMAG round robin comparison. The results confirm that the described setup can be used for specific total loss measurements of Epstein samples up to 1 kHz with expanded uncertainty of (0.5 up to 1.6) % for $k = 2$.

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